

EVALUATION OF SELF HEALING PERFORMANCE IN EPOXY/GLASS FIBER COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED USING VARTM

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ABSTRACT

Wind turbine blades are manufactured using the Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) method. These blades are subject to upwards of 10^8 - 10^9 loading cycles in a typical twenty year life span [1], which leads to the initiation and propagation of micro-cracks through the blade matrix material. Resin solvent healing using pre-synthesized solvent loaded double shell walled microcapsules is investigated for implementation into epoxy-based fiber-reinforced composite materials. Composite coupons are manufactured using the VARTM process, in which microcapsules are sprayed onto each ply prior to resin infusion. The effect of the resin flow on the migration and final distribution of microcapsules during the VARTM process is studied using fluorescence techniques. Mechanical performance of these coupons is characterized through a series of static tensile tests. Self-healing performance is quantified by performing quasi-static fracture on WTDCB (Width Tapered Double Cantilever Beam) specimens. Healing efficiency of specimens is calculated as a ratio of the Mode I fracture toughness of healed to virgin WTDCB specimens and indicates the degree of recovery.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wind turbine blades are typically fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites (PMCs) that are manufactured using glass fiber and epoxy resin. Blades installed on wind turbines experience a combination of static and dynamic loading which can have a significant impact on the lifetime reliability of the blades. The combination of these loads on the blade during operation leads to the formation of micro-cracks, which can propagate over time and lead to ultimate blade failure. Microscopic damage formation and propagation is currently undetected within turbine blades due to the difficulties in observing subsurface microscale (<100 μm) damage on a macroscale (~50 m) operating blade structure. Rather, blade damage is detected – typically via on-tower workers manually inspecting the blades – only once the damage propagates beyond a critical observable threshold [2].

Microcapsule-based self-healing technology has seen remarkable progress over the last decade in the utilization of various chemistries to recover mechanical properties. Much of the initial studies have investigated neat resins rather than fiber reinforced composite materials. Self-healing in fiber reinforced materials poses its own set of technical challenges because of the need for: a) microcapsules to survive the manufacturing process, b) smooth integration of the microcapsules into the fiber-matrix architecture and c) retention of original mechanical properties [5]. Self-healing in fiber reinforced composites has been demonstrated in a carbon fiber-epoxy composite by Kessler *et al.* (2003) using the dicyclopentadiene-Grubbs' catalyst chemistry. Jones *et al.* (2014) demonstrated recovery of interfacial shear strength in a glass fiber PMC using capsule-based resin solvent healing technology.

This paper will aim to investigate the effects of solvent-filled microcapsules on the VARTM processing of a glass fiber-epoxy composite and the impact that these microcapsules have on the mechanical properties of the composite. The approach of this research is to incorporate solvent-filled double shell walled microcapsules, first developed by Caruso *et al.* (2008), into a polymer matrix

composite. Solvent-based healing in an epoxy thermoset utilizes the residual amine functionality within the matrix to promote healing. The solvent swells the matrix to enable molecular diffusion of the residual amines in the matrix sol, making them available to unreacted epoxide groups for further curing [4]. Quasi-static fracture tests will be conducted using width tapered double cantilever beams (WTDCB) to obtain the mode I fracture toughness and these values will be used to quantify the healing efficacy of this capsule chemistry.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Microencapsulation Procedure

Double shell walled microcapsules containing ethyl phenylacetate were manufactured using an in situ polymerization in an oil-in-water emulsion technique [2]. Ethylene maleic anhydride (EMA) copolymer was mixed with deionized water and agitated at 500 RPM for 10 minutes. EMA is a surfactant that helps decrease the likelihood of microcapsules aggregating during the manufacturing process [7]. Following this mixing step, 2.5g of urea, 0.25g of resorcinol and 0.25g of ammonium chloride were added to the aqueous solution and mixed for 10 minutes at 800 RPM. After 10 minutes, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.5. The capsule core solution comprising ethylphenyl acetate (EPA) and an aromatic polyisocyanate (Desmodur L75) was then added to the aqueous solution. The EPA was dyed using 1 wt% red fluorescent dye. The solution was then emulsified for 10 minutes to allow the polyurea shell wall to begin forming at the water/EPA interface. 5.80 mL of 37 wt% aqueous formaldehyde was then added to the mixture and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 4 hours at 55°C. Upon completion, microcapsules were rinsed in warm water (55°C) and centrifuged. This process was repeated 3 times to remove excess EMA surfactant deposited on the outer surface of the capsule shell. The capsules were then filtered and dried for 24-48 hours. This manufacturing process has been outlined in Figure 1 below. EPA, urea, ammonium chloride, resorcinol, hexadecane and formaldehyde solution were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Desmodur L75 was donated by Bayer MaterialScience. Zemac E400 EMA was obtained from Vertellus Specialties Inc. and red fluorescent dye (DFSB-K149) was purchased from Risk Reactor Inc.

Figure 1: Manufacturing process for solvent-filled double shell walled microcapsules⁶

Figure 2a shows a scanning electron micrograph of the manufactured microcapsules and Figure 2b shows the size distribution of the microcapsules. The average diameter of the microcapsules was determined to be $54 \pm 19 \mu\text{m}$ using ImageJ software.

Figure 2: a) SEM image of solvent-filled microcapsules, b) Microcapsules have an average diameter of $54 \mu\text{m}$

The presence of ethylphenyl acetate (EPA) within the microcapsules was determined using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) as shown in Figure 3. The experiment was performed using a ramp rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The data shows that microcapsules retain more than 80% of their original mass below 220°C , which is the boiling point of EPA. At yet higher temperature, the capsules lose a significant portion of their original mass, indicating the capsules contain $\sim 90 \text{ wt\%}$ solvent.

Figure 3: Thermogravimetric analysis of double shell walled microcapsules containing ethylphenyl acetate. The vertical line at 220°C indicates the boiling point of the solvent, at which point 84 wt% of the capsule mass is retained.

2.2 Composite Panel Manufacturing

Composite panels were manufactured using the VARTM process. For the panels made using neat resin, four 30 cm x 25 cm rectangles were cut from the unidirectional glass fiber and stacked on top of each other on a glass plate to obtain samples that are 3.0 mm thick. System 2000 epoxy resin was then mixed with 2120 Epoxy Hardener (Fibreglast Corporation) in the ratio of 100:27, and infused into the glass fiber stack up. 2120 hardener provides a resin working time of 120 minutes and was chosen to ensure a long pot life for the infusion process. The panels were cured for 12 hours at room temperature followed by 12 hours at 35°C. It is important to recognize that this cure cycle was chosen because of the need for a partially cured/undercured specimen so that the solvent is able to extract any residual amine functionality from within the matrix. An aggressive post cure at a high temperature would render this self-healing chemistry ineffective. This procedure was used to manufacture two neat resin composite panels. Six 25.4 cm x 2.5 cm rectangular specimens were cut by waterjet from the first panel and used for tensile testing to obtain Young's modulus, tensile strength and Poisson's ratio. The second panel was used to obtain WTDCB (Width Tapered Double Cantilever Beam) specimens of the dimensions shown in Figure 4. These specimens were used to characterize fracture toughness of the composite material.

Figure 4: Dimensioned drawing of a WTDCB specimen with a taper ratio of 3. All dimensions are in mm

For the self-healing microcapsule loaded specimens, the ideal method to determine the mass of microcapsules incorporated into the composite specimens would have been to mix the 5 wt% microcapsules into the resin and infuse it into the composite. However, manufacturing composite specimens using this method poses a few challenges due to the textile architecture of the fabric and the infusion set-up for VARTM. The microcapsules used for this research work are likely insufficiently small to penetrate the interstitial spaces within the unidirectional glass fiber and ensure an even capsule distribution within the composite. During VARTM, porous peel ply is typically placed onto the top most layer of the fiberglass to ensure the vacuum bagging material does not stick to the composite once the part has cured and is demolded from the tool. The presence of porous peel ply increases the likelihood of microcapsules being filtered from the resin flow, thereby preventing their infusion into the composite.

The main aim of this research is to characterize healing efficiency of a composite loaded with solvent filled microcapsules, so an alternate spray coating-based approach was pursued to guarantee a uniform distribution of microcapsules within the specimen. The mass of microcapsules to be incorporated into the specimen was calculated based on the amount of resin present in the neat composite. The mass fraction of resin within the neat composite samples was characterized using a resin ignition test on 2.5 cm x 2.5 cm square specimens. The value obtained from the ignition test was

then scaled up to calculate the amount of resin that would be present in a 30 cm x 25 cm panel. 5 wt% of this value was calculated to determine the total mass of microcapsules to be used; the value was divided by three to obtain the mass to deposit in between each of the four plies of glass fiber. The microcapsules were then mixed with ethanol and added to the chamber of a gravity feed spray gun (Bostitch BTMT72393). Ethanol was chosen over more aggressive solvents like acetone and toluene because it does not cause the shell wall to disintegrate when it comes into contact with the microcapsules. Figure 5 shows the spray gun being used to distribute capsules over the area of the glass fiber. Figure 6 shows a sequential progression of microcapsules being sprayed onto one ply of the glass fiber. These images were captured using a longpass 590 nm UV filter attached to a 52 mm DSLR camera lens. Wavelengths below 590 nm are removed with this filter; because the capsules contain Texas Red dye (peak fluorescence ~610 nm), they are clearly visible in the images in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Spraying microcapsules onto each ply of the composite using a gravity feed spray gun

Figure 6: Microcapsules sprayed onto unidirectional glass fiber from left to right illuminate the stitching perpendicular to the unidirectional fibers. Dyed microcapsules are illuminated with UV light and images were captured using a DSLR camera with a long pass 590 nm filter attached to the lens.

Two panels were manufactured with embedded capsules. These panels were processed under the same cure conditions as the neat resin composite specimens. Six 25.4 cm x 2.5 cm rectangular specimens were cut from the first panel and used for tensile testing to obtain the Young's modulus, ultimate tensile strength and Poisson's ratio of the composite. The second panel was cut to obtain WTDCB (Width Tapered Double Cantilever Beam) specimens that were used to characterize fracture toughness and healing efficiency of the solvent-filled microcapsules.

Migration of microcapsules from their original position can lead to capsules being removed from the ply stack up as the resin leaves from the outlet valve. Moreover, a biased distribution of microcapsules within the composite can lead to an uneven distribution of mechanical properties of the manufactured specimen. Hence, to achieve a uniform distribution of capsules within the final composite structure, it is critical that the capsules do not migrate from the original position after the spray up process nor during VARTM infusion. The effect of the resin flow on the migration of microcapsules was investigated by using fluorescence imaging with a long pass filter fitted to a 52 mm DSLR camera lens. Figure 7 shows a progression of resin flowing through the composite. The bright spots in image "a" are the microcapsules fluorescing under UV light. It is evident from the series of images (b,c and d) that the bright spots do not shift from their original position as the flow front passes through that region. This demonstrates the robustness of the VARTM process when microcapsules are incorporated into the ply stack up.

Figure 7: (a) Overview image of the composite pre-form before infusion. Images (b), (c) and (d) show a chronological progression of the resin flow front during VARTM. The unchanged position of the two microcapsules in the zoomed in area shows that the resin flow front does not cause migration of microcapsules as it flows through the composite.

2.3 Characterization of Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties of the composite specimens were determined through a series of tensile and Width Tapered Double Cantilever Beam (WTDCB) tests as shown in Figure 8. The purpose of the tensile tests was to establish the degree to which the presence of microcapsules would alter mechanical properties such as Young's modulus, tensile strength and Poisson's ratio of the composite specimen. The WTDCB test was used to determine the impact of the presence of microcapsules on the Mode I fracture toughness, K_{IC} , of the composite specimen, as well as the healing efficiency of the solvent filled microcapsules.

Figure 8: Mechanical properties characterization in quasi-static loading: a) Tensile characterization and b) Mode I fracture toughness, K_{IC} , characterization in WTDCB geometry.

Table 1 shows a comparison of mechanical properties between neat and capsule loaded composite specimens. The data show that the presence of microcapsules does not negatively affect the static tensile properties of the composite specimens.

Table 1: Comparison of mechanical properties for composite specimens with and without microcapsules

Mechanical Property		Neat Composite	5 wt% capsule loaded composite
E_{11}	[GPa]	39 ± 2.5	39 ± 2.6
UTS	[MPa]	554 ± 53	556 ± 46
ν_{12}	–	0.22 ± 0.02	0.23 ± 0.02

WTDCB specimens were first introduced by Mostovoy [9] because of the difficulty in measuring crack length when conducting mode I fracture toughness experiments using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens. WTDCB specimens are crack length independent because of the tapered specimen geometry. The specimen taper is chosen to ensure that the ratio of the crack length and the width of the specimen always have the same ratio as seen in Figure 9. For a WTDCB, the mode I energy release rate is calculated using Equation 1.

$$G_{IC} = \frac{12P^2k^2}{E_{11}h^3} \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, G_{IC} is the Mode I energy release rate, P is the crack initiation load from the test, k is the

taper ratio of the WTDCB specimen, E_{11} is the tensile modulus in the fiber direction and h is half the thickness of the specimen. The mode I fracture toughness is then calculated using Equation 2.

$$G_{IC} = \frac{K_{IC}^2}{\left(\frac{E_{11}}{(1 - \nu_{12}^2)}\right)} \quad (2)$$

In Equation 2, K_{IC} is the Mode I fracture toughness and ν_{12} is the Poisson's ratio of the composite specimen.

2.4 Results and Discussion

WTDCB composite specimens were tested using an Instron 4464 Universal Testing Machine at a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. For both the neat and capsule loaded composite specimens, the virgin fracture toughness was obtained by recording load and displacement data from testing of the WTDCB samples. For the neat composite specimen, the samples were loaded until the crack propagated approximately 10 cm from the midpoint of the loading blocks, as shown in Figure 9. For the neat specimen, ethylphenyl acetate was manually injected into the crack plane and the specimen was unloaded and returned to its initial displacement on the testing machine. While still in its original position, the specimen was compressed with bar clamps, removed from the machine and allowed to heal undisturbed for 24 hours. The purpose of this *ex situ* healing experiment was to determine the maximum attainable efficiency for the solvent healing chemistry within a composite specimen.

Figure 9: Crack propagated to approximately 100mm from the centerpoint of the hole in the loading blocks. The taper ratio (a/b) stays constant as the crack propagates through the specimen.

For the capsule-loaded composite specimen, the sample was similarly unloaded, compressed with bar clamps, and healed for 24 hours. For both the *ex situ* and *in situ* healing, the healing efficiency (η) was calculated as the ratio of the mode I fracture toughness of the healed WTDCB specimen to the mode I fracture toughness of the virgin WTDCB specimen as shown in Equation 3 [4].

$$\eta = \frac{K_{IC}^{healed}}{K_{IC}^{virgin}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 10 shows the load vs. crack opening displacement of a neat composite sample. The peak load of the virgin specimen was recorded as 23.5 N. At this peak load, there was a sudden drop, indicating that the crack began to propagate through the specimen. Once the sample was fractured, 2-3 mL of EPA was injected into the crack plane and the WTDCB specimen was unloaded to its original position. The specimen was then clamped to allow the crack faces to make contact and let healing begin. The sample was allowed to cure for 24 hours and was re-tested to obtain the peak load for the healed specimen as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Comparison of virgin and healed peak loads for one neat composite WTDCB specimen cured through ex-situ healing.

The specimen did not show a drop in load at any point during the testing, which indicates that the specimen did not heal. There are three possible explanations for this observation: (a) the specimen did not contain sufficient residual amine functionality to allow the unreacted epoxide groups to cure. However, this possibility is unlikely since the post-cure was mild to ensure the presence of some unreacted amine groups; (b) the injected EPA leaked from the fracture plane prior to inducing healing; or (c) the cure time of 24 hours for the *ex situ* healing is too short a healing period. Further investigation will be conducted to verify which of these three best explains the loading curves in Figure 10.

Figure 11 shows the load vs. crack opening displacement of the microcapsule-loaded composite specimens. The peak load of the virgin capsule loaded specimen was recorded as 20.3 N; at this peak load, there was a load drop indicating that the crack began to propagate. Once the sample was fractured, the WTDCB specimen was unloaded to its original position and clamped to allow the crack faces to make contact for healing. The sample was healed for 24 hours, after which it was re-tested to obtain the peak load for the healed specimen as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Comparison of virgin and healed peak loads for microcapsule-loaded WTDCB specimen cured by *in situ* healing.

The peak load of the healed specimen was 2.43 N. While this value is low in comparison to the expected peak load when compared to healing performance of a neat epoxy specimen, the presence of some healing indicates that the hypothesis made earlier of the lack of residual amine can be ruled out as a possible explanation for why the *ex situ* healing experiment failed. The healing efficiency for the 5 wt% microcapsule loaded specimen was calculated to be 18% (see Table 2).

Table 2: Summary of Mode I fracture toughness and healing efficiency values for the neat and microcapsule-loaded specimens.

Specimen type	No. of specimens	K_{IC} virgin avg. (MPa m ^{0.5})	K_{IC} healed avg. (MPa m ^{0.5})	η_{max} avg (%)
Neat Composite (Ex-Situ Healing)	4	4.31	N.A.	0
5 wt% microcapsules (In-Situ Healing)	4	3.73	0.45	12

The values for the microcapsule loaded specimen indicate that healing is possible in a polymer matrix composite using the solvent healing chemistry. However, while Caruso and co-workers (2008) demonstrated full fracture toughness recovery of an epoxy matrix within 24 hours, a composite specimen is likely to require in excess of 48 or 72 hours to demonstrate significantly higher healing efficiencies than 12% as indicated in Table 2. Future work will focus on longer healing time periods. Challenges still exist in demonstrating fracture toughness recovery in an *ex situ* healed specimen. The inability to heal the specimen is attributed to the excess solvent leaving the specimen during the clamping process. Future experiments will focus on a smaller, yet better distributed amount of EPA in the crack plane.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Solvent-filled double shell walled microcapsules have been successfully incorporated into a composite specimen using resin infusion technology. The microcapsules can be incorporated into a composite specimen via the VARTM infusion process without inducing large-scale capsule migration during the resin flow. While this paper focuses on incorporating microcapsules into a composite using resin infusion technology, the resin used is not a resin specifically formulated for the wind industry. The solvent healing approach is demonstrated to recover a small fraction of fracture toughness in an under-cured glass fiber-epoxy matrix. Future work will focus on wind industry-specific matrix formulations, increased healing periods, and environmental aging studies to investigate whether composite can retain their fracture toughness properties over times relevant to the wind industry.

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